

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**DIAGNOSTIC ACCURACY OF TRANS ABDOMINAL
ULTRASONOGRAPHY FOR PREDICTION OF SCAR
DEHISCENCE IN FEMALES WITH HISTORY OF
CESAREAN SECTION**Dr. Ammara Ayub¹, Dr. Mashroof Abdullah², Dr. Syed Ahmer Gillani³¹Basic Health Unit Basal, District Attock²Demonstrator at Poonch Medical College, Rawalakot, Azad Jammu and Kashmir³Basic Health Unit Sharian Hattian Bala, Azad Jammu and Kashmir**Article Received:** July 2020**Accepted:** August 2020**Published:** September 2020**Abstract:**

Background: Trans abdominal ultrasonography is most commonly used to obtain images of hepatobiliary, urogenital, and pelvic structures. Sonographic measurement of lower uterine segment thickness near term has been shown to be correlated inversely with the risk at delivery of uterine scar defect. **Objective:** To assess the diagnostic accuracy trans abdominal ultrasonography for prediction of scar dehiscence in females with history of cesarean section taking cesarean section as gold standard. **Material & Methods:** This Cross-sectional study was conducted in Holy Family/Benazir Bhutto Hospital Rawalpindi during 2018 to 2019. Then females underwent transabdominal ultrasonography. Females labeled as positive or negative for scar dehiscence. At time of delivery, uterine scar assessed and scar dehiscence confirmed. **Results:** In this study the mean age of the patients was 30.22±6.33 years, 62(38.75%) patients had parity 02. The mean value of gestational age of the patients was 38.81±0.740 weeks. The sensitivity, specificity diagnostic accuracy of scar dehiscence on USG was 94.03%, 94.62% & 94.38% respectively taking cesarean section as gold standard. **Conclusion:** The transabdominal ultrasonography is a useful and reliable method having high value of diagnostic accuracy for prediction of scar dehiscence in females with history of cesarean section.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Ammara Ayub,**

Basic Health Unit Basal, District Attock

QR code

Please cite this article in press Ammara Ayub et al, *Diagnostic Accuracy Of Trans Abdominal Ultrasonography For Prediction Of Scar Dehiscence In Females With History Of Cesarean Section*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(09).

INTRODUCTION:

Cesarean section is one of the most frequent abdominal surgical operations carried out in the United Kingdom. The Cesarean section rate increased from 12% to 29% in the United Kingdom and from 21.2% to 30.1% in the USA between 1990 and 2008. The increasing Cesarean section rate and its associated complications has stimulated an interest in the behavior of Cesarean section scars and their associated potential morbidity.⁽¹⁾ The main cause of uterine rupture in a scarred uterus is lack of appropriate counseling and inadequate or absence of antenatal care with increasing number of women undergoing trial of labour after a previous caesarean section, in an anticipation of vaginal delivery, separation of previous caesarean scar has become a common cause of rupture especially in unskilled hands.⁽²⁾

One study showed that frequency of scar dehiscence present in 69% cases after previous cesarean section.⁽³⁾ The frequency of ruptured uteri was calculated to be 0.67%, giving a ratio of 1:148 deliveries.⁽⁴⁾ Ultrasound estimation of LUS provides a fairly simple and non-invasive method for prediction of scar dehiscence/rupture. Evaluation of thickness of LUS has been found to be a potential factor for predicting scar dehiscence⁽⁴⁻⁶⁾. The risk of scar dehiscence/rupture has been directly related to the thinning of LUS. However, there is controversy over the thickness of LUS.⁽⁷⁾ One study showed that the sensitivity and specificity of Transabdominal Sonography or transabdominal ultrasonography were 91% and 93% respectively for prediction of scar dehiscence.⁽⁸⁾ But another study showed that transabdominal ultrasonography showed the sensitivity 25%, specificity 100% for prediction of scar dehiscence.⁽⁹⁻¹¹⁾ One more study has showed that transabdominal ultrasonography showed the sensitivity 90.9%, specificity 52% for prediction of scar dehiscence.⁽¹²⁾

So the aim of this study is to assess the diagnostic accuracy transabdominal ultrasonography for

prediction of scar dehiscence in females with history of cesarean section taking cesarean section as gold standard.

OBJECTIVE:

To assess the diagnostic accuracy of trans abdominal ultrasonography for prediction of scar dehiscence in females with history of previous one cesarean section taking cesarean section as gold standard

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This Cross-sectional study was conducted in Holy Family/Benazir Bhutto Hospital Rawalpindi during 2018 to 2019. Sample size of 160 cases were calculated with 95% confidence level and taking expected percentage of scar dehiscence. Demographic information (name, age, gestational age, BMI, parity) was also obtained. Then females undergo transabdominal ultrasonography by a single senior radiologist had at least 4years' residency experience with assistance of researcher herself. Females were labeled as positive or negative for scar dehiscence (as per operational definition). Then females undergo cesarean section by researcher herself. At time of delivery, uterine scar was assessed and scar dehiscence was confirmed (as per operational definition). All this information was collected through proforma (attached).

Data Analysis

All collected data was entered and analyzed through SPSS 21. Quantitative variables like age, gestational age and BMI were presented by mean and SD. Variables like parity and scar dehiscence (on transabdominal ultrasonography and cesarean section) was presented by frequency and percentage.

RESULTS:

In this study total 160 patients were enrolled. The mean age of the patients was 30.22±6.33 years with minimum and maximum ages of 20 & 40 years respectively.

Table 01: Descriptive statistics of age (years)

Age (years)	n	160
	Mean	30.22
	SD	6.33
	Minimum	20
	Maximum	40

In this study, 21(13.13%) patients had parity 01, 62(38.75%) patients had parity 02, 53(33.13%) patients had parity 03 and 24(15%) patients had parity 04.

Fig#1: Frequency distribution of parity

The mean value of gestational age of the patients was 38.81 ± 0.740 weeks with minimum and maximum gestational ages of 38 & 40 weeks respectively (table 02). The mean value of BMI of the patients was 24.22 ± 3.321 kg/m² with minimum and maximum BMI values of 18.60 & 29.83 kg/m² respectively (table 03).

Table 02: Descriptive statistics of gestational age (weeks)

Gestational age (weeks)	n	160
	Mean	38.81
	SD	0.740
	Minimum	38
	Maximum	40

Table 03: Descriptive statistics of BMI (Kg/m²)

BMI (Kg/m ²)	n	160
	Mean	24.22
	SD	3.321
	Minimum	18.60
	Maximum	29.83

In our study scar dehiscence diagnosed positive by USG among 68(42.5%) patients whereas scar dehiscence diagnosed negative by USG among 92(57.5%) patients (table 4). In our study scar dehiscence diagnosed positive by cesarean among 67(41.88%) patients whereas scar dehiscence diagnosed negative by cesarean among 93(58.13%) patients.

Table 04: Frequency distribution of scar dehiscence diagnosed on USG

Scar dehiscence USG	Frequency		Percent
	Positive	68	42.5
Negative	92	57.5	
Total	160	100.0	

According to this study the sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV and diagnostic accuracy of scar dehiscence on USG was 94.03%, 94.62%, 92.65%, 92.65% & 94.38% respectively taking cesarean section as gold standard (table 05).

DISCUSSION:

This present cross-sectional study was carried out at department of Obstetrics & Gynecology, Lady Aitchison Hospital, Lahore to assess the diagnostic accuracy transabdominal ultrasonography for prediction of scar dehiscence in females with history of cesarean section taking cesarean section as gold standard. Cesarean section rates are increasing worldwide. As a result, women presenting with pregnancy with previous Caesarean Section are also rising. Previous Caesarean Section is becoming the most common indication for Caesarean Section, confirming the age-old dictum proposed by Edward Craigin in 1914 "Once a cesarean always a cesarean."

Various factors have been related to in-creased risk of scar dehiscence, including type of previous Cesarean section, surgical technique of closure of the uterine incision, intraoperative complications, as well as interval from previous Cesarean section, and estimated fetal weight in the current pregnancy.

In this study the sensitivity, specificity and diagnostic accuracy transabdominal ultrasonography for prediction of scar dehiscence in females with history of cesarean section was 94.03%, 94.62% & 94.38% respectively taking cesarean section as gold standard. Some of the studies are discussed below showing their results as.

CONCLUSION:

This study concluded that the transabdominal ultrasonography is a useful and reliable method having high value of diagnostic accuracy for prediction of scar dehiscence in females with history of cesarean section taking cesarean section as gold standard

REFERENCES:

1. Naji O, Abdallah Y, Bij De Vaate A, Smith A, Pexsters A, Stalder C, et al. Standardized approach for imaging and measuring Cesarean section scars using ultrasonography. *Ultrasound in Obstetrics & Gynecology*. 2012;39(3):252-9.
2. Zeb L, Bibi S. Trends in frequency and causes of uterine rupture in a tertiary care center between year 2001 and 2011. *Journal of Postgraduate Medical Institute (Peshawar-Pakistan)*. 2013;27(3).
3. Vikhareva Osser O, Jokubkiene L, Valentin L. High prevalence of defects in Cesarean section scars at transvaginal ultrasound examination. *Ultrasound in Obstetrics & Gynecology*. 2009;34(1):90-7.
4. Aziz N, Yousfani S. Analysis of uterine rupture at university teaching hospital Pakistan. *Pakistan journal of medical sciences*. 2015;31(4):920.
5. Sharma C, Surya M, Soni A, Soni PK, Verma A, Verma S. Sonographic prediction of scar dehiscence in women with previous cesarean section. *The Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology of India*. 2015;65(2):97-103.
6. Abosrie M, Farag MAEM. Prediction of cesarean section scar dehiscence before delivery using three-dimensional transabdominal ultrasonography. *Benha Medical Journal*. 2015;32(2):101.
7. Mohammed ABF, Al-Moghazi DA, Hamdy MT, Mohammed EM. Ultrasonographic evaluation of lower uterine segment thickness in pregnant women with previous cesarean section. *Middle East Fertility Society Journal*. 2010;15(3):188-93.
8. Caughey AB, Cahill AG, Guise J-M, Rouse DJ. Safe prevention of the primary cesarean delivery. *American Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology*. 2014;210(3):179-93.
9. Judith L, Debbie S, Sandra B. Counseling the nursing mother: a lactation consultant's guide. Canada Jones & Barlett publishers. 2010.
10. Yeniel A, Petri E. Pregnancy, childbirth, and sexual function: perceptions and facts. *International urogynecology journal*. 2014;25(1):5-14.